

Synthesis of Pyrano/Pyrido Benzothiophene Derivatives. Part—I

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A synthesis of 3-methoxycarbonylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-acetate and 2-formyl-3-methoxycarbonylbenzo[b]thiophene is reported. These key compounds have been converted into condensed heterocycles by standard methods.

THE impetus of the work reported herein arose from our success in the synthesis of 1H-pyrano-[3,4-b]benzofuran-1-one derivatives and their 2-aza analogues¹. Parallel exploratory studies were instituted with benzo[b]thiophene, a description of which forms the subject matter of the present paper.

Benzo[b]thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (I) which was prepared by a modified method of the earlier published method² was esterified with methanolic sulphuric acid to the dimethyl ester, which on controlled hydrolysis afforded the half-ester (II). Alternatively, the half-ester was obtained in good yield by the methanolysis of the anhydride³ of I. The pmr spectrum of II showed resonances at τ 1.5-2.9 for 4 aromatic protons, and singlets at τ 5.85 (3H, COOCH₃) and τ 3.1 (1H, COOH, exchangeable with D₂O). Confirmation of the structure is based on the identification of its decarboxylation product (III) which, on hydrolysis, afforded the known acid⁴ (IV). On homologation, the half-ester (II) afforded the di-ester (V) which showed absorptions at 1710 and 1740 cm⁻¹. The related acid (VI) (ν CO 1695, 1715 cm⁻¹) was obtained on alkaline hydrolysis. This di-acid, on treatment with acetyl chloride gave the anhydride (IX) which showed carbonyl absorptions at 1745 and 1780 cm⁻¹ (the ir data are similar to those observed in homophthalic anhydride).

- (I) R = R₁ = COOH
 (II) R = COOH, R₁ = COOMe
 (III) R = H, R₁ = COOMe
 (IV) R = H, R₁ = COOH
 (V) R = CH₂COOMe, R₁ = COOMe
 (VI) R = CH₂COOH, R₁ = COOH
 (VII) R = CH₂OH, R₁ = COOMe
 (VIII) R = CHO, R₁ = COOMe

The di-ester (V) on Stobbe condensation⁴ with benzaldehyde gave the related half-ester which, without isolation, was hydrolysed to give α -benzylidene-3-carboxybenzo[b]thiophene-2-acetic acid. This readily furnished the anhydride (X) (ν CO 1725, 1759 cm⁻¹) on treatment with acetic anhydride. The ester (V) on condensation with ethyl oxalate⁵ followed by the cyclisation of the resulting keto-ester and preferential decarboxylation gave the pyrano

carboxylic acid (XI) (ν CO 1700, 1730 cm⁻¹). On account of paucity of material (XI) its conversion into XII by ammonia was not possible.

The nitrogen analogue (XII) however was secured from the half-ester (II). The related acid chloride was reduced by NaBH₄ in dioxane to the alcohol⁶ (VII, ν_{max} 1710, 3420 cm⁻¹; yield, 67%). Experiments on the oxidation of the alcohol with activated manganese dioxide^{7,8} or chromic acid/pyridine⁹ led to the formation of I. Dehydrogenation of the alcohol however proceeded smoothly with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone (DDQ)¹⁰ when the aldehyde (VIII) was secured in good yield. The aldehydic ester on treatment with hippuric acid, sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave the related azlactone which on subsequent hydrolysis¹¹ with alkali gave the pyrido carboxylic acid (XII, ν CO 1660, 1700 cm⁻¹).

(IX)

(X)

(XI) x = O
 (XII) x = NH

Experimental

All m.p.s are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were measured as KBr disc and obtained with a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 237. The pmr spectrum was recorded in a Varian A-60 apparatus with TMS as internal standard.

Methyl benzo[b]thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylate: A solution of chloroacetic acid (2.84 g) was carefully neutralised with sodium carbonate solution (4 N) and added to a solution of benzo[b]thiophene-2,3-dione (4.53 g) in sodium carbonate solution (34 ml; 2 N) at 60-70° and the temperature maintained with stirring for 3 hr. On acidification, benzo[b]thiophene-2,3-

dicarboxylic acid (4.1 g), m.p. 250° separated. This was esterified with methanol (50 ml) containing sulphuric acid (2 ml) for 24 hr. The dimethyl ester crystallised from methanol in stout prisms, m.p. 91° (lit.⁹, m.p. 91°).

2-Methoxycarbonylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carboxylic acid: The foregoing ester (0.5 g) was refluxed with methanolic potash (1.2 ml; 10%) for 25 min. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in water. Any unchanged ester was removed with ether. On acidification and cooling, the half-ester separated as a cream coloured solid. This was collected, dried and crystallised from benzene and obtained as pale yellow needles (0.3 g), m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 55.8; H, 3.4. $C_{11}H_8O_4S$ requires C, 55.9; H, 3.4%).

Alternative method: Benzo[b]thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydride (m.p. 171°; ν_{CO} 1780, 1825 cm^{-1}) (1.0 g) was refluxed with dry methanol (5 ml) for 3.5 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue taken up in ether and extracted with saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution. This on acidification furnished the half-ester, m.p. 163°, in quantitative yield.

Benzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxylic acid: The foregoing half-ester (0.35 g) was intimately mixed with copper bronze (0.1 g) and the mixture distilled on a metal bath. Methyl benzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxylate (0.28 g) distilled at 165-66°/17 mm. This was hydrolysed without purification by boiling under reflux with sodium hydroxide solution (0.6 ml; 10%) for 1.5 hr. On acidification, the acid was obtained as a colourless solid in quantitative yield, m.p. 175-76° (lit.⁹, m.p. 174-75°). (Found: C, 60.4; H, 3.4. $C_9H_6O_4S$ requires C, 60.7; H, 3.4%).

Methyl 3-methoxycarbonylbenzo [b] thiophene-3-acetate: The half-ester (1.4 g) in dry benzene (6 ml) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (2 ml) for 3 hr. Benzene and excess of thionyl chloride were removed under reduced pressure and the resulting crystalline acid chloride (m.p. 61°) in dry ether was added to cooled ethereal diazomethane (from nitrosomethyl urea 6 g) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Removal of the solvent yielded the diazoketone as an oil which was taken up in dry methanol (30 ml) and heated on the water bath with a slurry of silver oxide (0.20 g) in methanol (20 ml) which was added from time to time until the evolution of nitrogen subsided (20 hr). The mixture was clarified by charcoal, filtered and solvent removed. The residue on distillation furnished a pale yellow oil (0.7 g) at 122-28°/0.3 mm which solidified. The ester crystallised from methanol in pale cream needles, m.p. 83°. (Found: C, 58.9; H, 4.5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4S$ requires C, 59.1; H, 4.6%).

3-Carboxybenzo[b]thiophene-2-acetic acid: The foregoing ester (0.25 g) was hydrolysed by boiling with NaOH solution (1 ml; 10%) for 2 hr. On acidification the related dicarboxylic acid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 235° (evolution of gas). (Found: C, 55.8; H, 3.4. $C_{11}H_8O_4S$ requires C, 55.9; H, 3.4%).

Anhydride. Pyrano(4,3-b)benzothiophene-1,3-(1H, 3H,4H)-dione: This was obtained by heating the dicarboxylic acid (0.1 g) with acetyl chloride (2 ml) for 4 hr. This crystallised from dry benzene in cream coloured needles, m.p. 204-5°. (Found: C, 60.5; H, 2.7. $C_{11}H_6O_8S$ requires C, 60.6; H, 2.8%).

α -Benzylidene-3-carboxybenzo[b]thiophene-2-acetic acid: A mixture of freshly distilled benzaldehyde (0.22 g) and methyl 3-methoxycarbonylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-acetate (0.53 g) was added to alcoholic sodium methoxide (sodium 0.05 g, methanol 4 ml) and refluxed for 6 hr. The residual mass after the removal of solvent was dissolved in water, extracted with ether to remove unchanged ester and then boiled with the addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide (3 ml; 10%) for 2 hr, cooled, and acidified. The sticky mass solidified on trituration with benzene. The compound (0.54 g) crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 208° (evolution of gas). (Found: C, 66.5; H, 3.7. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4S$ requires C, 66.7; H, 3.7%).

The anhydride was obtained by heating the dicarboxylic acid (0.1 g) with acetic anhydride (2 ml) for 10 min. This crystallised from benzene in deep yellow needles (0.06 g), m.p. 195°. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 3.2. $C_{18}H_{10}O_8S$ requires C, 70.6; H, 3.3%).

Condensation with ethyl oxalate: A mixture of ethyl oxalate (0.17 g) and methyl 3-methoxycarbonylbenzo[b]thiophene-3-acetate (0.27 g) was added to alcohol free sodium ethoxide (from sodium, 0.03 g) in dry benzene when the colour turned brown. The mixture was left overnight in the refrigerator and next day, dilute sodium hydroxide solution (1 ml; 1 N) followed by ether was added to it. The alkaline solution was separated, acidified and extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent the glyoxalyl derivative separated as an oil which was dissolved in acetic acid (0.5 ml) and treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.25 ml), warmed on the water bath for 30 min and cooled. After removal of volatile matter under reduced pressure, the brownish oily residue (0.15 g) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (1.5 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (0.8 ml) for 3 hr. A brown solid separated on cooling which was crystallised to give pyrano(4,3-b)benzothiophene-1-oxo-3(1H)-carboxylic acid which separated from alcohol in pale brown needles (0.1 g), m.p. 272°. (Found: C, 58.3; H, 2.3. $C_{13}H_8O_4S$ requires C, 58.6; H, 2.5%).

Methyl 2-Hydroxymethylbenzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylate: A solution of the half-ester (1.2 g) in dry benzene (5 ml) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (2 ml) for 3 hr. On removal of solvent, the resulting acid chloride was taken up in dry dioxane (0.8 ml) and added in instalments to a suspended mass of sodium borohydride (0.29 g) in dioxane (5 ml) with efficient stirring and left overnight with continuous stirring. Next day, the mixture was heated on a water bath for 8 hr, cooled and the complex decomposed carefully with iced dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting oil was taken up with ether, washed with $NaHCO_3$ solution and dried,

On removal of the solvent, the alcohol solidified. This crystallised from alcohol in colourless wooly needles (0.8 g), m.p. 193°. (Found : C, 59.5 ; H, 4.4. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3S$ requires C, 59.5 ; H, 4.5%).

Methyl 3-formylbenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxylate : The foregoing alcohol (0.66 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) was refluxed with DDQ (0.68 g) for 30 min and filtered hot. On removal of the solvent the aldehydic ester was obtained as a darkish oil. The 2,4-DNP crystallised from acetic acid as orange needles, m.p. 254-55° (decomp). (Found : N, 13.9. $C_{17}H_{12}O_6-N_4S$ requires N, 14.0%).

Azlactone : The foregoing aldehyde (0.45 g) was mixed with hippuric acid (0.5 g), fused sodium acetate (0.2 g) and acetic anhydride (1.2 ml). The mixture was heated on the water bath for 3 hr, cooled and filtered. The residue thus obtained was washed with alcohol affording the azlactone crystallising from acetic acid in silky yellow needles (0.35 g), m.p. 223°. (Found : C, 66.0 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 3.8. $C_{20}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires C, 66.1 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 3.9%).

Pyrido (4,3-b)benzothioiophene-1-oxo-3(1H, 2H)-carboxylic acid : The foregoing oxazolone (0.25 g) was heated with potassium hydroxide solution (4 ml ; 10%) for 2 hr. The clear yellow solution was cooled and acidified. The cream coloured solid which separated was washed with hot water and dried (0.16 g). The compound crystallised from

acetic acid in creamy needles, m.p. 354° (decomp). (Found : C, 58.5 ; H, 2.7 ; N, 5.7. $C_{13}H_7O_3NS$ requires C, 58.8 ; H, 2.9 ; N, 5.7%).

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